

Autonomous AI-enabled Industrial Sorting Pipeline for Advanced Textile Recycling

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Abstract—The escalating volumes of textile waste globally necessitate innovative waste management solutions to mitigate the environmental impact and promote sustainability in the fashion industry. This paper addresses the inefficiencies of traditional textile sorting methods by introducing an autonomous textile analysis pipeline. Utilising robotics, spectral imaging, and AI-driven classification, our system enhances the accuracy, efficiency, and scalability of textile sorting processes, contributing to a more sustainable and circular approach to waste management. The integration of a Digital Twin system further allows critical evaluation of technical and economic feasibility, providing valuable insights into the sorting system’s accuracy and reliability. The proposed framework, inspired by Industry 4.0 principles, comprises five interconnected layers facilitating seamless data exchange and coordination within the system. Preliminary results highlight the potential of our holistic approach to mitigate environmental impact and foster a positive shift towards recycling in the textile industry.

Index Terms—Textile recycling, Autonomous systems, Computer vision, Artificial intelligence, Industry 4.0

I. INTRODUCTION

Textile waste has become a pressing global concern, with today’s overconsumption and throwaway cultures contributing significantly to escalating volumes of discarded textiles. The global clothing and footwear consumption is expected to surpass 100 million tonnes by 2030, while in the European Union, approximately 5.8 million tonnes of textile are discarded every year [1]. The environmental impact of this waste is detrimental, including consequences in resource depletion and pollution, that underscore the urgent need for innovative waste management solutions.

Leading cause for this problem, is the linear production and consumption model that has been traditionally associated with the fashion industry [2]. This approach has significantly contributed to the textile waste crisis, as it lacks integration of effective recycling processes. The problem has been further amplified by the rapid evolution of fashion trends, which

inevitably leads to shorter garment lifespans. While attempts to limit this crisis have been made, current methods that rely on manual sorting are inefficient, labor-intensive, and often prone to errors, thus hindering the transition towards a more sustainable fashion industry [3].

Besides the direct environmental concerns of textile waste, the magnitude of the problem also presents a missed opportunity for significant resource recovery and development of circular economy practices. To address this issue, a new paradigm of automated textile analysis pipelines is required, integrating automation, artificial intelligence (AI), and computer vision into the basis of textile recycling systems [4]. Therefore, in this work our aim is to tackle the inefficiencies in traditional textile sorting by introducing a state-of-the-art autonomous textile analysis pipeline.

Our system utilises robotics, spectral imaging, and AI-driven classification, to enhance the accuracy, efficiency, and scalability of textile sorting processes, thus contributing to a more sustainable and circular approach to textile waste management. Notably, our approach is complemented by a Digital Twin (DT) system, that enhances the associated processes by allowing the critical evaluation of their technical and economic feasibility. Moreover, through the integration of data from the AI-driven models, the DT provides valuable insights into the accuracy and reliability of the sorting system. Through this holistic approach, we aim to mitigate the environmental impact of fabric waste and assist in the industry’s shift towards a more positive approach to recycling.

In addition, our autonomous textile analysis pipeline incorporates laser segmentation to optimise the production of textile fractions tailored for diverse recycling processes. This approach allows precise cutting of materials, enabling the removal of components such as buttons and zippers, thus enhancing the efficiency of the sorting system by ensuring that the resultant fractions are well-suited for repurposing. This

targeted segmentation further contributes to the development of a more sustainable and resource-efficient textile waste management system.

Comprising five interconnected layers, the architectural framework of our introduced pipeline allows the seamless exchange of data and coordination within the system. This interconnected approach in conjunction with the Digital Twin insights, leads to the development of the desired sustainability in our model, aligned with the principles of Industry 4.0.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II explores related work on textile analysis. Section III presents the methodology of our approach by describing the system architecture, subsystems, and the AI models that drive the automated textile analysis pipeline. Section IV presents the results of the AI-driven process and highlight the role of the Digital Twin towards the feasibility analysis. Finally, section V summarises key findings and emphasises the impact of our system.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Textile Analysis

Textile analysis systems encompass a wide range of techniques and methods for evaluating various aspects of textiles. These systems typically involve both objective and subjective testing methods, including the use of instrumental techniques and multi-analytical approaches to study and identify textile component materials, such as spectroscopy [5] and chemometrics [6]. To address the registration challenge arising from the utilisation of multiple sensors with diverse modalities in spectral analysis, subpixel solutions, due to resolution variations have been introduced [7]–[9]. Other approaches to detect and recognise textile materials are based on photometric techniques [10] offering precise visualisation of the fabric patterns. Textile analysis plays a vital role in evaluating fabric waste generation and conservation methods, including the qualitative and quantitative analysis of post-consumer textile waste [11].

State-of-the-art textile classification methods involve the use of spectral analysis and AI for accurate categorisation of textile samples. Spectroscopic techniques in particular, can rely on near-infrared spectroscopy and pattern recognition methods such as soft independent modelling of class analogy, least squares support machines, and extreme learning machines, for classifying textile fabrics [12]. In addition, the associated spectra can be analysed through statistical multivariate methods, achieving high speed and accuracy in classification [13], thus facilitating textile recycling processes. Spectral analysis can also utilise the periodicity and orientation inherent in fabric texture, to detect defects. One-dimensional Power Spectral Density analysis using an Auto-Regressive estimation model has been proposed to differentiate normal from defective textures in woven fabrics [14].

The integration of AI with spectral analysis represents a significant advancement, offering enhanced capabilities for precise identification and classification of textiles, thus addressing the evolving challenges in industrial applications. AI

can be applied to perform feature extraction, compression, and dimensional reduction of the data in raw spectra [15], keeping the most relevant information, reducing computational complexity, and enhancing the efficiency of subsequent processing. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have emerged as a powerful tool in medical applications, enabling tasks such as disease diagnosis from medical images [16]. CNNs have also been utilised to improve identification and sorting of waste textile based on near-infrared spectral data [17]. By integrating such AI-driven models, the system is capable of real-time classification, while achieving an accuracy above 95%, in less than 2 seconds per sample. CNNs can also handle composite materials that involve binary mixtures of common textile fibres, processing the related spectral data to identify patterns and extract relevant features for the accurate classification [18].

B. Textile Analysis Datasets

Textile analysis datasets have been introduced, mostly targeting tasks related to defect detection. The AITEX Fabric Image Database [19] is a publicly available dataset comprising 245 images that include 105 defective samples in 12 categories, and 140 defect-free samples. Overall, the database involves 20 different fabric types with a region of interest of 256 x 256 pixels. Focusing on anomaly detection, the MVTec Anomaly Detection dataset [20] consists of 3629 images allocated across 15 distinct categories designated for training and validation, with an additional 1725 images assigned for testing purposes. The training set, includes only defect-free images. In total, five categories of regular and random texture are included. In addition, a comprehensive resource for fabric detection tasks is the ZJU-Leaper dataset [21]. This database encompasses 98,777 samples, featuring 27,650 instances with defects and 71,127 normal samples, representing a total of 19 diverse fabric types.

While fabric defect detection databases are available, the current landscape of publicly available datasets dedicated to textile type recognition appears to be sparse. Several works have developed and annotated custom data in this context, including popular commercial fabrics [22] and blended textiles [23]. However, the absence of openly available textile material datasets has hindered the development of robust recognition algorithms, capable of generalising in real-world applications of sorting and recycling pipelines. This underscores the need for creation and sharing of such resources to facilitate advancements in this domain of textile analysis.

C. Autonomous Integrated Textile Analysis

The integration of robotics in cloth manipulation [24] has recently seen a significant rise, highlighting the potential for enhancing the efficiency and accuracy in textile analysis and sorting by automating handling tasks, while ensuring precision and reducing human errors. Despite these advancements, a comprehensive and holistic approach to automated textile sorting, integrating both robotics and AI with computer vision, is not widely documented in the existing literature. Many

Fig. 1. Autonomous textile analysis pipeline architecture.

studies focus on individual aspects, such as spectral analysis or AI-driven classification, rather than a cohesive integration of these technologies into an automated textile sorting pipeline. In the near future, the potential of 6G on the Internet of Things [25] could empower these pipelines with even greater capabilities, by embedding sensor technology that could allow real-time data collection on various textile properties. This data, processed through ultra-fast 6G networks, could further refine AI algorithms for automatic material identification and optimise robotic manipulation based on specific fabric characteristics.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this section we outline the summary of our developed approach. The methodology is divided into the system architecture, the classification method, including the dataset and training, and the Digital Twin system.

A. Architecture

The architecture of the autonomous textile analysis pipeline consists of five building blocks:

- 1) Intelligence Layer
- 2) Sensing Layer
- 3) Information Layer
- 4) Visualisation and Execution Layer
- 5) Repository Layer

The Intelligence Layer functions as a central hub for the aggregation of data and information derived from the Information Layer, incorporating additional contextual insights such as metadata sourced from the underlying infrastructure and the Repository Layer. Furthermore, this layer establishes a seamless connection with the Sensing Layer to acquire multispectral or other relevant multimodal data, using a spectral camera and other sensors. The collected data is then utilised to execute AI-driven tasks, employing computer vision and machine learning methodologies for the identification, classification, and segmentation of the textile materials.

The outcomes, along with relevant model information, are subsequently transmitted to the Repository Layer, facilitating the storage of obtained results for subsequent analysis. The Information Layer encompasses a comprehensive suite of predictive analytics underpinned by the Digital Twin system and meta-information. Ultimately, the Visualisation and Execution Layer undertakes the presentation of outcomes and all related information, by integrating system management processes and providing visual representations. The overall architecture is demonstrated in Figure 1.

B. AI Classification

1) *Training dataset:* The employed dataset comprises cloth images, sourced from [26]. The images were annotated using a sensor capable of discriminating among nine distinct categories of apparel. The data acquisition process employed a HinaLea camera, which captured imagery across 151 spectral bands. These bands span the wavelength range of 950 nm to 1700 nm, with increments of 5nm, encompassing both near-infrared and infrared spectral regions. Data across five material types, including cotton, polyester, silk, wool, and viscose were provided, as presented in Figure 2.

2) *Convolutional neural networks:* At the core of our textile recognition pipeline CNNs play a central role, utilising their intrinsic capability to proficiently capture spatial hierarchies and patterns in data. Textile fabrics often exhibit complex visual structures with repeating patterns and textures. CNNs excel at learning hierarchical features through the use of convolutional layers, which apply filters to small local regions of the input data, allowing them to detect low-level features like edges and textures. Their ability to recognise patterns irrespective of their spatial positioning make them appropriate for real-world use cases, in which shifts and rotations in images are prevalent.

In our study we investigated two custom architectures, and two state-of-the-art pretrained models, fine-tuned in our specific dataset. For the pretrained models, EfficientNet [27]

TABLE I
CNN MODEL SUMMARIES.

Model	Layers #	Parameters #
EfficientNet B6	~600	~41 million
ResNest-101	~600	~46 million
Medium Custom	22	~1.5 million
Simple Custom	10	~1.5 million

and ResNest [28] were selected, due to their wide success across a variety of image classification tasks. A summary of each model is presented in Table I.

C. Digital Twin System

The integration of the Digital Twin is a critical aspect of our autonomous textile sorting pipeline, as it serves as the virtual counterpart to the physical sorting system, combining real-time data, predictive models, and simulations to replicate and enhance the system dynamics. The DT enables predictive analysis for proactive issue identification, algorithm optimisation, and parameter fine-tuning, thus facilitating superior efficiency and accuracy in the associated textile classification.

Moreover, the DT functions as a controlled training ground for the CNN models, allowing iterative testing and refinement

Fig. 2. Dataset class distribution.

Fig. 3. Digital Twin visualisation.

TABLE II
DIGITAL TWIN KEY PARAMETERS.

Parameter	Range
Conveyor belt speed	1-5
Robotic arm speed	1-5
Camera capture time	3-8
Laser segmentation speed	1-5

without constant adjustments to the physical system. Its role extends to fault detection, providing a versatile platform for extensive scenario testing, and ultimately elevating the robustness and reliability of the autonomous textile sorting processes. Table II outlines the main parameters of the DT. For each parameter, there is a setting with respect to the simulated percentage error, ranging from 0-100 %. A visualisation of the DT is presented in Figure 3.

IV. EVALUATION

This section examines the performance and efficacy of the introduced autonomous textile sorting pipeline. It presents the key metrics used to provide insights into the model's ability to accurately categorise textiles and their respective results. IN addition, the evaluation includes the integration of the Digital Twin and investigates its role in enhancing the system's efficiency and reliability.

A. Classification Results

In assessing the classification performance, precision, F1 score, and accuracy serve as the key benchmarks.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}, \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}, \quad (2)$$

where TP , TN , FP , and FN are the true positive, true negative, false positive, and false negative samples respectively.

$$\text{F1 Score} = \frac{2 \cdot \text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (3)$$

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In addition to the above metrics, ROC-AUC and confusion matrices are also considered. ROC-AUC describes the area

TABLE III
TEXTILE CLASSIFICATION RESULTS.

Model	Accuracy	Precision	F1 Score
EfficientNet B6	0.242	0.219	0.195
ResNest-101	0.586	0.670	0.618
Medium Custom	0.393	0.078	0.113
Simple Custom	0.363	0.082	0.114

Fig. 4. ResNest confusion matrix.

under a Receiver Operating Characteristic curve. It provides a single value that represents the ability of the model to distinguish between positive and negative instances. The confusion matrix describes the TP , TN , FP , and FN through a visual representation.

The results of the models across the key metrics are outlined in Table III. The scores highlight suboptimal performance across all models, with the exception of the ResNest which was fine-tuned after data augmentation. The EfficientNet B6 model demonstrates limited accuracy at 0.242, while precision and F1 scores also remain modest. The Medium Custom and Simple Custom models, although displaying higher accuracy, exhibit notably low precision and F1 scores. The ResNest model was able to achieve the highest accuracy, reaching 0.586, with more robust precision and F1 scores of 0.670 and 0.618 respectively. Overall, these results underscore the need for further refinement and optimisation of the classification models to enhance their effectiveness in accurately categorising textile fabrics within the sorting system. The confusion matrix corresponding to the ResNest model is depicted in Figure 4. In the matrix, labels 0-4 correspond to cotton, polyester, wool, silk, and viscose. Figures 5 and 6 show the ROC-AUC curves for all the models. The values are mostly in the range of 0.5, again leaving room for improvement.

B. Digital Twin Results

For the evaluation of the Digital Twin system we configured the conveyor belt and robotic arm speed to 5, camera capture speed to 3, and laser segmentation speed to 5. Three experiments were conducted with 10, 12, and 14 clothes assigned for analysis by the system. Each instance was executed 10 times with an 8% error chance. The average outcomes of the experiments are presented in Table IV. Note, that the camera capture time metric includes the AI inference time. These results underscore the DT's efficacy in simulating

(a) EfficientNet

(b) ResNest

Fig. 5. ROC-AUC curves for the EfficientNet and ResNest models.

(a) Medium custom

(b) Simple custom

Fig. 6. ROC-AUC curves for the Medium and Simple custom models.

and evaluating the dynamics of our textile sorting system, providing valuable insights into its operational efficiency and performance metrics.

The outcomes of this research hold significant promise for broader applications beyond the textile industry. The core technologies employed, such as AI classification and spectral imaging, demonstrate transferability to other sectors that rely on sorting or quality control processes. This includes industries like waste management, where accurate identification of ma-

TABLE IV
DIGITAL TWIN RESULTS.

Number of clothes	10	12	14
Total time	80.7 s	80.3 s	93.6 s
Conveyor belt time	18.3 s	12.7 s	14.8 s
Robotic arm time	22.4 s	19.6 s	22.8 s
Camera capture time	30 s	36 s	42 s
Laser segment time	10 s	12 s	14 s
Green production efficiency	75%	75%	75%

materials is crucial for proper recycling streams, and agriculture, where efficient sorting of crops and produce can optimise yield and quality. Furthermore, the pipeline's architecture is built on Industry 4.0 principles, allowing for scalability. Thus, the system can be readily adapted to handle larger volumes of data and materials, making it suitable for deployment in bigger facilities or for applications with significant throughput.

In addition, by enabling predictive analysis and continuous algorithm optimisation through the DT system, this approach can significantly improve efficiency and accuracy across various industries. This translates to potential cost savings, reduced waste, and improved overall operational performance. Additionally, the DT system can minimise the need for physical prototyping, further contributing to sustainability efforts. Finally, the focus on sustainable textile waste management within the pipeline serves as an inspiration for similar green practices in other fields. By promoting the efficient sorting and potential reuse of materials, this approach aligns with the principles of a circular economy, where resources are kept in use for extended periods. The success of this pipeline in the textile industry paves the way for the development of analogous sustainable solutions in diverse sectors, contributing to a more environmentally friendly future.

V. CONCLUSION

This study addresses the critical challenge of escalating textile waste by presenting a cutting-edge autonomous textile analysis pipeline. The integration of robotics, spectral imaging, AI-driven classification, and laser segmentation has been instrumental in enhancing the accuracy, efficiency, and scalability of textile sorting processes. Our architectural framework, characterised by Industry 4.0 principles, facilitates the seamless data exchange and coordination, forming the basis for a sustainable and circular textile waste management paradigm. While early findings highlight the need for refinement of the classification models and the training data, insights provided by the Digital Twin already show the potential of the automated sorting pipeline for a transition to a greener economy. The incorporation of the laser segmentation further optimises the recycling processes by automating the removal of components such as buttons and zippers.

This holistic approach contributes to the development of a more resource-efficient recycling system. The impact of our work extends beyond technological advancements, as it

addresses environmental concerns associated with textile waste and supports the fashion industry's shift towards a more positive recycling approach. The proposed pipeline, assisted by the Digital Twin insights and AI features, lays the groundwork for a transformative and sustainable future in textile waste management.

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